

Effect of Aqueous Ethanol Leaf Extract of *Anacardium occidentale* On Liver and Kidney Parameters of Albino Wistar Rats

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Abstract-: *Anacardium occidentale* is a cashew plant which the leaves are used for therapeutic purposes in Nigeria and other parts of the world. This study was aimed at determining the toxic effect of the aqueous ethanol leaf extract on the liver and the kidney of albino wistar rats. 27 adult albino wistar rats were used. 3 were used for acute toxicity (up and down procedure) at 5000mg/Kg body weight, while 24 were used for sub-acute toxicity, grouped into 6 animals per group. Group 1 (control), group 2, 3, and 4 were dosed with 100, 250 and 400mg/Kg body weight of the extract respectively. The percentage yield of the extract was 44.66%, while the phytochemical analysis of the extract showed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, phenolic compound and Tannins, while steroid is absent. The LD₅₀ showed no mortality or sign of toxicity at the dose of 5000mg/Kg body weight in rats used. When compared with the control group, the percentage body weight showed decrease in weight as the days of administration increase from 7 to 14 days. Relative organ (liver) body weight ratio of all the treated rats showed non-significant ($p > 0.05$) difference from the control while the relative organ (kidney) body weight ratio of groups 2 and 3 also showed non-significant ($p > 0.05$) difference, but group 4 showed significant ($p < 0.05$) difference. The AST, ALT, ALP, Bilirubin, Total protein and Albumin in the liver of the treated rats showed non-significant ($p > 0.05$) difference from the control, while the kidney parameters, Creatinine and chloride showed non-significant ($p > 0.05$) difference, but Urea, Na⁺, and K⁺ showed significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in groups 3 and 4 of the treated rats. The results of sub-acute study suggest that the extract may not be toxic to the liver, but toxic to the kidney at 250 and 400 mg/Kg body weight after the 14 days administration.

Keywords: Phytochemicals, Acute toxicity, Sub-acute toxicity, Cashew leaves, hepatotoxic

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1.0 Introduction

In recent years, the population of individuals using different plant extracts for treatments and preventions of diseases are increasing significantly. Famurewa *et al.*, (2018) reported the 2004 world health organization (WHO) estimation of about 80% populations in Asian and African countries which depend on herbal medicines for their primary health care. Apart from the economic situation of the people in the developing countries which makes most people go for alternative medicine, Ovioun *et al.*, (2022) also reported that increase in the use of plant based medicine may be due to the discovery that extracts from plants are pharmacologically safe and contain a diverse array of secondary metabolites with therapeutic values. Al-Ahmad *et al.*, (2024) also reported that the use of medicinal herbs has skyrocketed in the last decades owing to their availability, low cost, agreement with patients' values, and perceived safety and efficacy in preventing,

managing, and treating several chronic diseases whose burden is increasing worldwide. The safety of most of these plants have not been established due to lack of standardized procedure for their consumptions/administration, which raise a serious concern among health care giver. Okonkwo *et al.*, (2010), also observed in a short communication that the therapeutic values of most of the herbs are indisputable but their toxicities sometimes limit their clinical uses and thus, the toxicity profile of these herbs must always be considered especially as the doses and dosing regimens of their preparations are not usually determined.

Cashew tree commonly known as *Anacardium occidentale* is a plant which is most popular in Nigeria because of its fruits and nut. It's a tree very useful as different parts of it are used either individually or collectively with other plants to treat several diseases. It is a multipurpose tree of the Amazon that grows up to 15 m high. The bark and leaf of the tree are used medicinally, and the fruit has international appeal and market

value as food (Okonkwo *et al.*, 2010). The local name of the fruit in Yoruba is kaju, in Hausa is kasu and in Igbo is kashuu. Researches have shown that the leaf extracts of *Anacardium occidentale* has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects (Souza *et al.*, 2017; Oviosun *et al.*, (2022). The cashew leaf and cashew leaf extract enriched with zinc have been reported as a good source of antidiarrhoeal agents (Udedi *et al.*, 2013). Leaf extract prevent lead acetate-induced liver and kidney toxicity by decreasing oxidative stress and inflammation in rats (Aminu *et al.*, 2023). Research studies on the ethanolic leaves extract of *Anacardium occidentale* have been reported to show effect on haematological and biochemical parameters of albino rats (Saidu *et al.*, 2020). Ethanol leaves extract have also been reported to have a negative effect on the body weight of rats, but may serve as immune system booster (Iyare *et al.*, 2017). The daily administration of aqueous extract of stem bark of cashew tree have been reported to alter liver and kidney status to exhibit toxic effects at higher dose in rat (Famurewa *et al.*, 2018). Dave *et al.* (2020) reported the toxic effect of methanol leaf extracts of *A. occidentale* at high concentrations after 21 days of Administration. The aim of this study is to determine the phytochemicals present in aqueous ethanol leave extract, lethal dose (LD₅₀) of the extract, effect of the extract on body weight, organ body weight ratio and liver and kidney parameters of albino wistar rats.

2.0 Material and Method

2.1 Plant Material Collection and Identification

Anacardium occidentale leaves were collected from the Botanical Garden of in Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano. Plant was authenticated and deposited in the Herbarium Unit of the Department of Plant Biology, Bayero University, Kano, Kano State, Nigeria with the Voucher Specimen of BUKHAN 0296.

2.2 Extraction of Plant Materials

Preparation of *A. occidentale* leaves extract was conducted in the Department of Biochemistry and Forensic Science, Faculty of Sciences, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano State, Nigeria. The under-shade air-dried leaves were pulverized into powder. About 500g of the powder was macerated in 3.0L of aqueous ethanol (50% ethanol and 50% water). After 4 days with interval shaking, the solution was

filtered using Whatman No 1 filter paper and evaporated to dryness using oven at 70°C (degree Celsius). The percentage yield calculated using the following formular: Yield (%) = $\frac{\text{Weight of the extract Gotten}}{\text{Weight of the Powder Taken}} \times 100$

2.3 Phytochemical screening

The protocols of Harbone, (1998), Gupta *et al.* (2013), Somit *et al.* (2013) and Yumnamcha *et al.* (2014), were used for detection of the different phytochemicals present in the aqueous-ethanol extract of *A. occidentale* leaves.

2.4 Experimental Design

2.4.1 Acute Toxicity (LD₅₀)

Acute toxicity (LD₅₀) study of the aqueous-ethanol extract was carried out using up and down procedure. Three albino rats with the weight of 159.7g, 176.6g and 198.0g were randomly picked and were administered 3.2ml, 3.5ml and 4ml of 250mg/ml of the extract respectively, the three rats were carefully observed for 24hours, to see any signs of toxic effect at the highest dose of 5000mg/kg (OECD, 2001).

The doses administered were calculated using the following formula:

$$V(\text{ml}) = \frac{D \times B}{C}$$

Where

V: Volume

D: Dose used (mg/kg body weight)

B: Body weight (Kg)

C: Concentration (mg/mL)

2.4.2 Sub-Acute Toxicity Study

Twenty-four (24) albino wistar rats were selected by stratified randomization and then divided into four groups of six each and treated for 14 days as follows: Group I (Control group): received distilled water only, Group II, Group III and Group IV received 100mg/kg, 250mg/kg and 400mg/kg of extract respectively. The first day of dosing was taken as day 0 and blood was collected on day 14 and used for biochemical analysis (Salawu *et al.*, 2019).

2.4.3 Percentage Body Weight and Relative Organ Body Weight Ratio

The body weight of each rat was expressed using a calibrated weighing balance during the acclimatization period, once before the commencement of dosing, during the period of dosing and on the 14th day before the animals were sacrifice (Salawu *et al.*, 2019). After sacrificing the animals, the liver and the kidney of each animals was removed, weight taken and compared with their body weight.

2.4.4 Collection of Blood

Blood samples were collected by the orbital technique. Blood sample for biochemical analysis was collected from the retrobulbar plexus of the medial canthus of the eye to enable outflow of blood into labeled centrifuge tubes, allowed to clot and centrifuged for 15 minutes at 3000 rpm to separate serum and the serum was used for biochemical analysis.

2.4.5 Determination of Biochemical Parameters

The analysis was carried out to determine the serum concentrations of creatinine, urea, Na⁺, K⁺, Cl⁻, total protein, albumin, bilirubin, and activities of liver enzymes such as alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) using standard laboratory procedure.

3.0 Statistical Analysis

The data obtained were presented as the mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), Graph pad instant software (San Diego, USA) was used to compare means across the groups. Mean values with p < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Results

4.1.1 Percentage Yield

Percentage yield after the extraction of *Anacardium occidentale* leaf using aqueous-ethanol solvents in the ratio of 1:1 (v/v), the percentage yield for the crude extract was 44.66% (w/w) (Table 1).

Table 1: Percentage yield of aqueous-ethanol leaves extract of *A. occidentale*

	aqueous-ethanol leaves extract
Weight of leaves (g)	500
Weight of Extract after evaporation (g)	223.3
Percentage yield (%)	44.66

4.1.2 Phytochemical Results

Table 2 showing the qualitative phytochemical compounds present in aqueous-ethanol leaves extract of *A. occidentale*, which includes alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenolic compounds and saponins, while steroids are absent.

Table 2: Phytochemical present in aqueous-ethanol leaves extract of *A. occidentale*

Phytochemical compounds	Sign	Remarks
Alkaloids	+	Present
Flavonoids	+	Present
Saponins	+	Present
Phenolic Compounds	+	Present
Tannins	+	Present
Steroids	-	Absent

4.1.3 Acute Toxicity Study (LD₅₀)

In the acute toxicity of the aqueous-ethanol extract, the rats dosed with 5000mg/Kg body weight of the extract showed no signs of toxicity and no death was recorded after 24 and 48 hours (Table 3).

Table 3: Medial lethal dose (LD₅₀) of aqueous-ethanol leaves extract of *A. occidentale*

Dosed	Number of rats	Number of Death
5000mg/Kg	1	0
5000mg/Kg	1	0
5000mg/Kg	1	0

4.1.4 Percentage Body Weight

The body weight of the rats dosed with extract for 14 days showed a decrease in weight as the concentrations increases from 7 and 14 days when compared with the control group (Table 4).

Table 4: Effect of aqueous-ethanol leaves extract of *A. occidentale* on body weight

Grouping	7 days Weight gain (%)	14 days Weight gain (%)
Control	21.44	5.34
100mg/Kg	-5.47	-6.25
250mg/Kg	-9.45	-8.94
400mg/Kg	-5.97	-12.94

Negative percentage indicates weight loss: Weight gain was calculated using the formular: % Weight gain =

$$\frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

4.1.5 Relative Organ Body Weight

The effect of the extract on the relative organ body weight shown on Table 5, where the liver showed non-significant (p > 0.05) difference in all the treated groups, while the kidney showed a

significant ($p < 0.05$) difference from the control at 400mg/Kg body weight.

Table 5: Effect of aqueous-ethanol leaves extract of *A. occidentale* on Organ body weight ratio

Grouping	% Organ weight ratio (Liver)	% Organ weight ratio (Kidney)
Control	3.553±0.34 ^a	0.72±0.04 ^a
100mg/Kg	3.873±0.37 ^a	0.89±0.07 ^a
250mg/Kg	4.155±0.20 ^a	0.82±0.10 ^a
400mg/Kg	4.468±0.92 ^a	0.95±0.12 ^b

The value is presented as mean ± SEM; (n = 6), values with the same superscript as control are non-significant ($p > 0.05$) difference; The % organ body weight was calculated using the formular:

$$= \frac{\text{Organ weight}}{\text{Body weight}} \times 100$$

4.1.6 Effect of Aqueous-ethanol Extract on Liver Function Parameters

Table 6: Effect of aqueous-ethanol leaves extract of *A. occidentale* on Liver Parameters

Grouping	AST (u/l)	ALT (u/l)	ALP (u/l)	Bilirubin (mg/dL)	Total protein (g/L)	Albumin (g/L)
Control	10.50±0.29 ^a	8.1±1.08 ^a	42.0±7.42 ^a	4.7±0.28 ^a	87.7±2.68 ^a	58.1±0.96 ^a
100mg/Kg	9.50±0.50 ^a	6.8±1.00 ^a	46.67±6.89 ^a	4.9±0.19 ^a	90.4±3.27 ^a	58.0±1.85 ^a
250mg/Kg	10.37±0.24 ^a	7.4±0.71 ^a	44.13±3.48 ^a	4.7±0.28 ^a	85.1±1.48 ^a	56.0±1.29 ^a
400mg/Kg	10.37±1.03 ^a	7.8±0.71 ^a	46.1±4.03 ^a	4.6±0.27 ^a	90.1±3.27 ^a	56.3±1.48 ^a

Values are presented as mean ± SEM; (n = 6), values with the same superscript as control are non-significant ($p > 0.05$) difference.

Table 7: Effect of aqueous-ethanol leaves extract of *A. occidentale* on Kidney Parameters

Grouping	Creatinine (mg/dl)	Urea (mg/dl)	Sodium (mmol/L)	Potassium (mmol/L)	Chloride (mmol/L)
Control	35.80± 1.34 ^a	2.48± 0.26 ^a	65.60±1.14 ^a	11.740±2.56 ^a	139.38± 8.76 ^a
100mg/Kg	35.00±0.71 ^a	2.40± 0.07 ^a	68.40 ±0.89 ^a	12.10±0.47 ^a	167.62±7.88 ^a
250mg/Kg	36.80±2.36 ^a	3.31± 0.19 ^b	139.60±6.46 ^b	14.68±1.06 ^b	128.80±11.63 ^a
400mg/Kg	38.80±2.34 ^a	4.08± 0.16 ^b	154.60±3.50 ^b	16.68±0.19 ^b	129.50±4.96 ^a

Values are presented as mean ± SEM; (n = 6), values with the same superscript as control are non-significant ($p > 0.05$) difference.

5.0 Discussion

Herbal medicinal plants are believed to be an important source of new chemical substances with potential therapeutic effects (Oyesina and Salihu, 2011), where promising solvents were used for the extraction of the active compounds. The use of solvent in extracting the component of the plant is very important in the field of herbal medicine. In this research, aqueous

It was observed that repeated daily oral administration of the extract at 100, 250 and 400 mg/Kg body weight for the period of 14 days did not show significant ($p > 0.05$) difference in the serum levels of AST, ALT, ALP, Bilirubin Total protein, and albumin of the treated groups compared with the control group (Table 6).

4.1.7 Effect of Aqueous-ethanol Extract on Kidney Function Parameters

The effect of aqueous-ethanol leaves extract of *A. occidentale* on the serum levels of creatinine, urea, Na⁺, K⁺ and Cl⁻ are presented in table 7. The creatinine, and Cl⁻ levels in all the treated groups show non-significant ($p > 0.05$) difference from the control, while urea, Na⁺, and K⁺ in groups 3 and 4 animals dosed with 250 and 400mg/Kg of the extract show significant ($p < 0.05$) difference from the control.

ethanol was used, and 44.66% of the extract was gotten (Table 1), which was very good yield when compared to Konan and Bacchi, (2007) who reported 26.11% in ethanol leaf extract, while Onasanwo *et al.*, (2012) reported 1.67%, 1.17%, 20%, and 23.3% from hexane, dichloromethane, methanol and aqueous solvents respectively. Varghese *et al.*, (2013), also reported 16.9% and 12.8% (w/w) in aqueous and methanol extract. Phytochemicals are enriched

with different pharmacological activities, and these activities have a potential to be used for therapeutic purpose (Afzal *et al.*, 2023). The qualitative analysis of phytochemicals in the aqueous-ethanol leaves extract showed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, phenolic compound, and tanins, while steroid was absent (Table 2). This is in accordance with the works of Varghese *et al.*, (2013) and Anaziah, (2023) who reported the presence of carbohydrates, tannins, saponins, resins, alkaloids and flavonoids in cashew leaves extracts. The LD₅₀ of the aqueous-ethanol extract is above 5000mg/Kg (Table 3). In the acute toxicity (LD₅₀) of the extract, no death was recorded after 24hours of administration. Observation of the animals for another 48hours showed no form of delayed toxicity and no mortality was observed, which indicated that the extract may be safe. 5000mg/Kg is above the safety limits given by Konan and Bacchi, (2007), where 2000mg/Kg was reported for ethanol leaf extract, while 4525mg/kg was reported for aqueous leaf extract by Iyare *et al.*, (2017) and Anaziah, (2023) also reported same value for ethanol extract. Okereke *et al.*, (2020) reported the LD₅₀ of cashew nut shell oil (CNSO) to be 1000mg/Kg. The part of the plants, type of solvents used and route of administrations may have aided the observed difference. The LD₅₀ values help in determining the safest dose to be used in the main experiments. The percentage body weight gains and relative organ weight has been used as an indicator of adverse effects of xenobiotic such as drugs and chemicals (Salawu *et al.*, 2019). In this research, the percentage body weight gains were negatively affected by the extract, where there were reductions in weights of all the treated rats when compared with control as the doses and duration of administration increases from days 7 to 14 (Table 4). This indicated that, the extract may have inhibited the normal growth process, or the reductions in weights may have been due to reduction in food intake (loss of appetite) or poor metabolism of the ingested food. Bioavailability of protein may be prevented by the presence of tannin in the extract (Table 2), and this can also be the cause of observed decrease in weight gain (Alagbaoso *et al.*, 2015; Salawu *et al.*, 2019). This result is in accordance with the work of Iyare *et al.*, (2017), who have also reported the negative effects of ethanol leaves extract on the body weight of the treated rats. The relative organ weight ratio for the liver in the treated

groups showed non-significant ($p > 0.05$) difference from the control, while the kidney at the highest concentration administered (400mg/Kg) showed significant ($p < 0.05$) difference (Table 5). Ramakrishna *et al.* (2015) in Ijioma *et al.* (2018) reported that organ weight can be one of the most sensitive indicators of an effect of a test substance as significant differences in organ weights between treated and untreated (control) animals may occur in the absence of any morphological changes. The changes observed in relative organ weights in kidney of the treated group may be due to the observed body weight changes. Hence any slight decline in body weight without corresponding effect on the organ weight will lower the relative organ weight values. The changes observed in the 400mg/Kg treatment group may be due to mild enzyme induction in the organs. It has been reported that minimal increase in liver weights without any microscopic lesion can be correlated with enzyme induction (Ramakrishna *et al.*, 2015). Liver toxicity is measured based on activity of ALT, AST, ALP, total protein, albumin and bilirubin. An elevated level of AST, ALT, and ALP in serum have been reported as an indication of hepatocellular disruption, due to the damage to structural integrity of the liver which is deranged or compromised, leading to leakage of these enzymes from the cytosol into the bloodstream (Ighodaro and Omole, 2010; Salawu *et al.*, 2019), while the bilirubin is an important metabolic product of the blood with biological and diagnostic values (Ighodaro and Omole, 2010). Total protein and albumin can be used as markers for assessing the functional capacities of the liver (Pendota *et al.*, 2010). The non-significant ($p > 0.05$) difference in all these parameters in rats treated with the extract suggest that the sub-chronic administration of this extract does not seriously affect hepatocyte function in the rats or induce any serious cytotoxic damage to the liver at the tested dose. This result is in contrast with the reports of Iyare *et al.* (2017) and Saidu *et al.* (2020) where the ethanol leaves extract was reported to have an effect on the liver parameters, while in agreement with the work of Konan *et al.*, (2007) who also reported that ethanol leaf extract have no effect on the ALT and AST. The work of Dave *et al.*, (2020), also reported the liver toxicity of methanol leaves extract of *Anacardium occidentale* in albino rats. The kidney functioning capacity was assessed by measuring the levels of electrolytes, creatinine, and urea in the serum of the animals. The non-

significant ($p > 0.05$) effect of the extract on the serum Cl^- and creatinine of the animals suggest that the normal functioning of the kidney in relation to these parameters were unaffected. However, the significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in the level of urea, K^+ and Na^+ in groups 3 and 4 may have suggested kidney dysfunction (Table 7). There was no significant reduction in total protein (Table 6), which may have led to increase in urea a bi-product of protein catabolism; the observed increase in urea, K^+ and Na^+ levels at 250 and 400mg/Kg body weight may suggest impaired kidney function of the animals. It may also be an indication of dysfunction at the glomerular and tubular levels of the kidney (Pendota *et al.*, 2010; Salawu *et al.*, 2019). This significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in urea, K^+ and Na^+ levels of the animal dosed 250 and 400mg/kg body weight indicate dose and parameter specific effect of the extract since other parameters were not significantly altered at other dose levels (Pendota *et al.*, 2010). The pharmacological and toxicological activity of most herbal medicines has been linked to the presence of alkaloids, triterpenoids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, and other compounds in the herbs (Otemenyin *et al.*, 2013).

6.0 Conclusion

The results obtained in this study indicated that the aqueous-ethanol leaves extract of *A. occidentale* have lethal dose (LD_{50}) above 5000mg/Kg and may have no toxic effect on the liver, but dose-specific effects on the kidney at 250 and 400 mg/Kg body weight. Therefore, it is impossible that the functions of the kidney as a major role in filtration, absorption, secretion and excretion may be adversely affect by the extract.

Author Contribution

The author has the sole contribution to this article.

Conflict of Interest

The author has no conflict of interest.

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